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Implementation of Distance Learning Delivery in Tinoc District

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Abstract

One hundred fourteen teachers in Tinoc revealed notable findings on pedagogy, technology, instruction and assessment used during the distance learning. Descriptive statistics, frequency, mean and ANNOVA were used. Teachers used distribution of printed modules, easy-to-use technology in instruction and assessment such as laptops, smart phones, key pad cellphones and hand-held radios were utilized including printed test with written examinations for assessment. When grouped by gender, there was a significant difference on pedagogies like the use of the distribution of printed modules and modules shared through an application. Technology, instruction and assessment had no significant difference to the respondents. When grouped by position, pedagogy and assessment reveals a significant difference on the distribution of printed modules and use of group chat or messenger and printed test and written examination respectively. When grouped by the number of years in service, pedagogy and assessment had a significant difference on teacher-parent-learner interaction and the use of printed and written test respectively. There is no significant difference on the technology and instruction used. Problem felt by teachers were late submission of modules, no parents and guardians to assist the children at home, residence of learners, and educational attainment of parents who were hard up in teaching their children, and unanswered modules. Learners let their modules be answered by their abled parents or siblings but scored low in the summative test. Learners were found to be poor readers and did not demonstrate instructional reading level.

Keywords: pedagogy, assessment, instruction, distance learning, modules, technology

1.0 Introduction

Distance learning, as a chosen learning modality in Ifugao, is a first-time experience to teachers. This is a new trend of educating children too. This also requires many adjustments to teachers from being trained in classroom learning to home schooling. Department of Education Ifugao Division conducted trainings in support to distance learning delivery. Through research the Department of Education (DepEd) Ifugao Division can gauge the return of investment (ROI) in terms of trainings since DepEd spent big amount of money for capability, retooling, upskilling and training of teachers. Spending a lot of money proves that the DepEd officials believe in the principle that human resource is one of the very important assets of the department.

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With this endeavor, the DepEd can achieve its vision of attaining quality education in the country as a whole. As a reward of this goal, the investments must have a positive and productive return of gainful results.

However, this vision attain quality education among children has been obstructed or disturbed by the effect of the so-called pandemic on Coron Virus (COVID-19). Despite this crisis, the Department of Education pushes that education must continue.

Teaching in the so-called Distance Learning Delivery (DLD) is a trial or experimental for teachers. This means that teachers will apply what they have learned from their previous trainings and translate their learnings into a useful and functional teaching strategies, approaches, activities and knowledge. Example on computer literacy. All the skills, knowledge and learning must be converted for the use in the distance education such as power point presentatin to video podcast, video making and the like so that they can give these to their learners. Teaching strategies must also be translated into how can these strategies be still useful in a modular learning modality.

This study focused on three important data that supported implementation of distance learning delivery (DLD) such as pedagogy, technology, instruction, and assessment. From the ranked problems felt by the teachers, intervention program could also be determined.

In Tinoc district, distance learning delivery was embraced by teachers so there is a need to establish data on pedagogy, technology, instruction and assessment they used and design intervention program to whatever challenges they experienced. With these, the investment and the money spent by the government to teachers would not be wasted but can result to multiple outputs such as quality teachers and quality education of learners.

2.0 Methodology

2.1 Research Design

The study utilized descriptive survey research design. The data gathered were subjected to descriptive statistics and drew out quantities describing the pedagogy, technology, instruction and assessment to which teachers can express their perception on the implementation of distance learning delivery. Frequency counting was undertaken to consolidate the problems felt by the respondents.

2.2 Research Locale

The study was carried out in Tinoc, Ifugao.

2.3 Research Participants

The total population as respondents in the study were the 120 k-6 primary and elementary public school teachers and the 24 Graddes 7-10 teachers in the secondary schools in Tinoc District. Students and parents were selected for interviews to validate the perception of the main respondents.

2.4 Research Instrument

This study used a newly constructed survey questionnaire.

2.5 Data Gathering Procedure

This study used the survey questionnaire which was constructed by the researcher. Interviews were done to establish a realistic data.

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2.6 Ethical Considerations

This researcher observed proper protocols and demonstrated honesty in the conduct of the study. The data collected were dealt with utmost confidentiality. Acknowledge the support which is a great concern from the respondents.

3.0 Results and Discussion

Table 1.a presents the Gender of Respondents. The data reveals that female teachers or 94.4% out of 114 actual respondents actively participated in the implementation of distance learning delivery in the district. It can be gleaned from the data that there were only 8.8% male respondents. This means that when it comes to module distribution, they were not enough to do it. On the other hand, female respondents were obliged to deliver also their modules to where their students were if students or parents did not come to get their modules in the drop off areas. One problem felt by the teachers here was the problem on transportation since there were no regular trips in every barangay or sitio.

Table 1.a. Gender of Respondents

Gender	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Male	10	8.8	8.8	8.8
Female	103	90.4	90.4	99.1
Neutral	1	.9	.9	100.0
Total	114	100.0	100.0	

Table 1.b presents the position of the respondents. Data shows that 100% of the teachers implemented the distance learning in the district. Further, 45.6% of the teacher 3 were mostly involved in the distance learning delivery followed by teacher 1. It can be gleaned from the data that with their positions, they coped with the challenges on the paradigm shift from face to face classes teaching strategies to distance learning.

Table 1.b Position of the Respondents

Position	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
T1	42	36.8	36.8	36.8
T2	16	14.0	14.0	14.0
T3	52	45.6	45.6	45.6
MT1	2	1.8	1.8	1.8
MT2	1	.9	.9	.9
Neutral	1	.9	.9	100.0
Total	114	100.0	100.0	

Table 1.c. presents the number of years in service of the respondents. Data shows that teachers having below 10 years up to 20 years teaching experiences were active implementers of distance learning. In reflection, they supported the learning modality and brought this into completion.

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Table 1.c Number of Years in Teaching of the Respondents

Number of Yea Teaching	Frequenc	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
10 & below	65	57.0	57.0	57.0
11-20	35	30.7	30.7	87.7
21-30	11	9.6	9.6	97.4
31-40	3	2.6	2.6	100.0
Total	114	100.0	100.0	

Table 2 presents the significant difference in the extent of implementation of Distance Learning Delivery in terms of pedagogy. Data reveals that the pedagogies implemented by the teachers were distribution of printed modules, calling learners individually, teacher-parent-learner instruction. This means that learners printed modules and distributed them to parents. Further, they had instructed the parents regarding the activities of the learners in the modules and later called the learners individually to assist them or further explain the directions, lessons and performance tasks.

Pedagogies with low implementation by the teachers were the use of audio or video learning materials and group chats/messenger in discussing the lesson. Data shows that only those with strong and stable internet connectivity can use this learning modality. Hence, teachers who facilitated learning in schools with no internet connectivity used other learning modalities like two-way radios or home visitation observing health protocols.

On the other hand, teachers did not use pedagogies 3,4, and 7. These were the use of virtual classroom, use of application such as KineMaster, Filmix, among others, and output videos of learners in terms of performance tasks. This is true because virtual classroom needs stable internet connectivity so the teachers did not attempt to use it. Non-usage of mobile application in teaching for other teachers with no internet signal during the distance learning was caused by computer complex steps in editing recorded videos. These needs expertise to guide skill-recipient teachers. Other factors which discouraged teachers to use mobile applications were the noise of the environment during recording time. This needed also much time to prepare. Teachers also did not use the output videos in gathering performance task results of learners. According from an interview with a Grade 8 learner, they were ashamed with their voice and for some instances, unavailability of smartphones of learners.

Table 2.a Extent of Implementation of Distance Learning Delivery in Terms of Pedagogy

Pedagogy	N	Mean	Standard Deviatid	Interpretation base Mean
p1	114	3.9035	.29657	MI
p2	114	3.0351	.93080	MI
p3	114	1.5439	.91342	NI
p4	114	1.9825	1.21919	NI
p5	114	2.4737	.89453	LI
p6	114	1.3596	.69291	NI
p7	114	1.77281	.91482	NI
p8	114	3.3947	.84789	MI

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p9	114	2.3947	1.20190	LI
Valid N				
(likewise)	114			

Legend:

- 4=Highly Implemented (HI)
- 3=Moderately Implemented (MI)
- 2=Low Implementation (LI)
- 1=Not Implemented (NI)

Table 2.b. presents the extent of implementation of teachers on Distance Learning Delivery in terms of Technology. Data shows that only technology 1 or the use of computer and laptop were moderately used technologies during the distance learning delivery by the teachers. This means that at least had basic knowledge on this gadget which were used on designing and localizing as well as printing of modules.

Technologies with low implementation were smart phone, keypad phones and hand-held radios. This means that teachers can only use these gadgets when internet connectivity is not available in their respective teaching stations. This opposed the finding of Graham (2006) that online tools are being used in the distance learning. Further, the use of hand-held radios also needs open space. It can be gleaned from the data that these technologies will still be used in the future teaching so teachers must be prepared to use these technologies. According from Bringas (2022), used technologies during the distance learning is irreversible. This means that teachers will be forced to embrace the use and enhance their skills for its full utility.

Table 2.b. Extent of Implementation on Distance Learning Delivery in terms of Technology

Technology	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Tech 1	114	3.0877	1.16407
Tech 2	114	2.8596	1.21114
Tech 3	114	2.7632	1.19958
Tech 4	114	2.2105	1.11684
Valid N (likewis	114		

Legend:

- 4=Highly Implemented (HI)
- 3=Moderately Implemented (MI)
- 2=Low Implementation (LI)
- 1=Not Implemented (NI)

Table 2.d presents the Extent of Implementation on Distance Learning Delivery in terms of Instruction. Data shows that modules were moderately used by teachers during the implementation of distance learning. This is because this mode of instruction was chosen by Schools Division Office of Ifugao. However, this is not highly implemented due to the use of other learning modalities by other teachers with weak internet connectivity.

Teachers did not use online, television, and radio-based instruction in Tinoc district. In fact, due to weak internet signals online learning was not possible. The use of television and radio-based

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instruction were not also possible during the distance learning. This means that scheduled lessons in the television were not included as instruction of teachers. Thus, assessment of lesson was not done too. Radio station was not yet established in the municipality. Hence, teachers had no interest to use this during their instruction.

The result opposed the idea of Malipot (2020) that other learning modalities were utilized distance learning to reduce the cost of printing modules.

Table 2.d Extent of Implementation of Distance Learning Delivery in terms of Instruction

Instruction (i)	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
i1	114	3.9211	.27085
i2	114	1.2982	.67745
i3	114	1.2895	.66150
i4	114	1.5526	.92260
Valid N (likewise)	114		

Table 2.e. presents the Extent of Implementation of Distance Learning Delivery in terms of Assessment. Data shows that teachers moderately used distribution of printed test with written examinations. This proves the idea of Keles and Ozel (2016) that data and written text are still used in distance learning. This means that teachers had other technologies like printers, photocopying machines and computers/laptops.

Google forms, outputs in video, Kotobee, and word wall were not utilized by teachers during the distance learning delivery. It can be gleaned from the results that teachers' needs in terms of trainings will include the use of these identified assessment tools. In reflection, only those who are teaching in schools with strong internet connectivity can be trained.

Table 2.e. Extent of Implementation of Distance Learning Delivery in terms of Assessment

Assessment (a)	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
a1	114	3.8509	.35778
a2	114	1.4035	.81707
a3	114	1.7895	.90694
a4	114	1.2632	.56526
a5	114	1.4825	.90458
Valid N (likewise)	114		

Table 3.a presents the significant difference in the extent of implementation of Distance learning delivery in terms of pedagogy when grouped by gender. Data reveals that Pedagogies 1 and 4 were significant to teachers. This means that teachers moderately used distribution of printed modules and modules shared through an application. Example, a teacher in Araling Panlipunan (AP) shared modules through ShareIt or Bluetooth to learners with smartphones. This means that cost of printed modules was lessened due to its possibility. In reflection, the use of these two (2) pedagogies depends on the gender of the teachers.

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Table 3.a. Significant Difference in the Extent of Implementation of Distance Learning Delivery in terms of Pedagogy when grouped by gender

Technology	N	Levene's Test for Equality of Variances	
		F	Significance Level
p1	Equal Variances Assumed	6.561	.012
	Equal variances not assumed		
p2	Equal Variances Assumed	.758	.386
	Equal variances not assumed		
p3	Equal Variances Assumed	.983	.324
	Equal variances not assumed		
p4	Equal Variances Assumed	4.237	.042
	Equal variances not assumed		
p5	Equal Variances Assumed	.074	.786
	Equal variances not assumed		
p6	Equal Variances Assumed	3.457	.066
	Equal variances not assumed		
p7	Equal Variances Assumed	1.184	.279
	Equal variances not assumed		
p8	Equal Variances Assumed	1.223	.271
	Equal variances not assumed		
p9	Equal Variances Assumed	.138	.711
	Equal variances not assumed		

Table 3.b. presents the significant difference in the extent of implementation of Distance learning delivery in terms of technology when grouped by gender. Data reveals that when it comes to the use of technology, both identified genders can use either any of the available technology procured for the school. This means that desktop computers and laptops are not gender-specific gadgets.

Table 3.b. Significant Difference in the Extent of Implementation of Distance Learning Delivery in terms of technology when grouped by gender

Technology	N	Levene's Test for Equality of Variances	
		F	Significance Level
t1	Equal Variances Assumed	.075	.785
	Equal variances not assumed		
t2	Equal Variances Assumed	1.254	.265
	Equal variances not assumed		
t3	Equal Variances Assumed	.190	.664
	Equal variances not assumed		
t4	Equal Variances Assumed	.056	.813
	Equal variances not assumed		

Table 3.c. presents the significant difference in the extent of implementation of Distance Learning Delivery in terms of assessment when grouped by gender. Data shows that assessment is not specific. This means that all assessments were utilized by both male and female teachers during

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the distance learning. In reflection, male and female shared whatever assessment tools they had at hand.

Table 3.c. Significant Difference in the Extent of Implementation of Distance Learning Delivery in terms of assessment when grouped by gender

Instruction	N	Levene's Test for Equality of Variances	
		F	Significance Level
i1	Equal Variances Assumed	.684	.410
	Equal variances not assumed		
i2	Equal Variances Assumed	.005	.947
	Equal variances not assumed		
i3	Equal Variances Assumed	2.817	.096
	Equal variances not assumed		
i4	Equal Variances Assumed	2.258	.136
	Equal variances not assumed		

Table 3.d. presents the significant difference in the extent of implementation of Distance Learning Delivery in terms of Pedagogy when grouped by position. Results show that pedagogies are significant based from the position of teachers. At Alpha level or 0.05 level of significance, distribution of printed modules and use of group chat or messenger involved position of respondents. This means that use of these pedagogies is dependent on the position of teachers. Hence, school administration can also include this finding in their planning with teachers especially that the significance focused on pedagogy 1 and 8. Further, teachers either used printed or messenger as their strategy in distance learning.

Table 3.d. Significant Difference in the Extent of Implementation of Distance Learning Delivery in terms of Pedagogy when grouped by gender

Pedagogy		ANOVA				Sig.
		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	
p1	Between Groups	1.278	5	.256	3.188	.010
	Within Groups	8.660	108	0.80		
	Total	9.939	113			
p2	Between Groups	3.344	5	.669	.764	.578
	Within Groups	94.515	108	.875		
	Total	97.860	113			
p3	Between Groups	3.168	5	.634	.751	.587
	Within Groups	91.113	108	.844		
	Total	94.281	113			
p4	Between Groups	2.128	5	.426	.277	.925
	Within Groups	165.837	108	1.536		
	Total	167.965	113			
p5	Between Groups	1.225	5	.245	.297	.914
	Within Groups	89.196	108	.826		
	Total	90.421	113			

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p6	Between Groups	.366	5	.073	.147	.981
	Within Groups	53.888	108	.499		
	Total	54.254	113			
p7	Between Groups	2.393	5	.479	.561	.730
	Within Groups	92.177	108	.853		
	Total	94.570	113			
p8	Between Groups	13.014	5	2.603	4.120	.002
	Within Groups	68.223	108	.632		
	Total	81.237	113			
p9	Between Groups	10.851	5	2.170	1.538	.184
	Within Groups	152.386	108	1.411		
	Total	163.237	113			

Table 3.e. presents the significant difference in extent of implementation of Distance learning Delivery in terms of technology when grouped by position. Data shows that technology can possibly used in any teachers' current position. Further, teacher 1 to master teacher 2 embraced technology as their tools in delivering learning to learners. Thus, technology is not position specific. In reflection, teachers tried using computer, laptop, smart phones, keypad cell phones, and hand-held radios during the distance learning differently in different locations depending on internet connectivity or its absence. Thus, teachers enhanced their knowledge on the use of these technologies.

Table 3.e. Significant Difference in the Extent of Implementation of Distance Learning Delivery in terms of technology when grouped by gender

Technology		ANOVA				Sig.
		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	
t1	Between Groups	7.454	5	1.491	1.105	.362
	Within Groups	145.668	108	1.349		
	Total	153.123	113			
t2	Between Groups	5.850	5	1.170	.790	.559
	Within Groups	159.905	108	1.481		
	Total	165.905	113			
t3	Between Groups	9.923	5	1.985	1.404	.229
	Within Groups	152.682	108	1.414		
	Total	162.605	113			
t4	Between Groups	1.407	5	.281	.218	.954
	Within Groups	139.540	108	1.292		
	Total	140.947	113			

Table 3.f. presents the significant difference in the extent of implementation of Distance Learning Delivery in terms of Assessment when grouped by Position. Data shows that assessing learners using printed and written as assessment 1 is significant. This is below the level of significance of 0.05. This means that between groups of teachers, printed test and written examination is dependent per position. Further, printed and written assessment is still very much useful and helpful to teachers in assessing learning outcomes of learners.

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Table 3.f. Significant Difference in the Extent of Implementation of Distance Learning Delivery in terms of Assessment when grouped by gender

Assessment		ANOVA				Sig.
		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	
a1	Between Groups	2.541	5	.508	4.603	.001
	Within Groups	11.924	108	.110		
	Total	14.465	113			
a2	Between Groups	.943	5	.189	.274	.927
	Within Groups	74.495	108	.690		
	Total	75.439	113			
a3	Between Groups	2.163	5	.433	.515	.765
	Within Groups	90.785	108	.841		
	Total	92.947	113			
a4	Between Groups	1.275	5	.255	.791	.559
	Within Groups	34.830	108	.323		
	Total	36.105	113			
a5		6.994	5	1.399	1.767	.126
		85.471	108	.791		
		92.465	113			

Table 3.g. presents the significant difference in the extent of implementation of Distance Learning Delivery in terms of Pedagogy when grouped by number of years in service of the respondents. Data shows that the pedagogy 8, based on level of significance at 0.05, on teacher-parent-learner interaction is significant to teachers depending on the number of years in service value the importance of interaction between teachers with parents and learners as well. This is proven by the problems felt by teachers that they are requesting the conduct of limited face to face with learners so that they can interact with one another and learn intently with the learners.

Table 3.g. Significant Difference in the Extent of Implementation of Distance Learning Delivery in terms of pedagogy when grouped by number of years in service of the respondents

Pedagogy		ANOVA				Sig.
		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	
p1	Between Groups	.371	3	.124	1.421	.240
	Within Groups	9.568	110	.087		
	Total	9.939	113			
p2	Between Groups	3.271	3	1.090	1.268	.289
	Within Groups	94.589	110	.860		
	Total	97.860	113			
p3	Between Groups	6.650	3	2.217	2.783	.044
	Within Groups	87.631	110	.797		
	Total	94.281	113			
p4	Between Groups	5.482	3	1.827	1.237	.300
	Within Groups	162.482	110	1.477		
	Total	167.965	113			
P5	Between Groups	2.294	3	.765	.954	.417

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	Within Groups	88.127	110	.801		
	Total	90.421	113			
P6	Between Groups	2.661	3	.887	1.891	.135
	Within Groups	51.593	110	.469		
	Total	54.254	113			
P7	Between Groups	.441	3	.147.856	.172	.915
	Within Groups	94.129	110	.856		
	Total	94.570	113			
P8	Between Groups	6.382	3	2.127	3.126	.029
	Within Groups	74.855	110	.680		
	Total	81.237	113			
P9	Between Groups	4.628	3	1.543	1.070	.365
	Within Groups	158.609	110	1.442		
	Total	163.237	113			

Table 3.h. presents the significant difference in the extent of implementation of Distance Learning Delivery in terms of technology when grouped by number of years in service of the respondents. Data shows that there is no significant difference between serving through the years or new or old teachers proved that they are the real technology or instruments of learning to learners.

Table 3.h. Significant Difference in the Extent of Implementation of Distance Learning Delivery in terms of technology when grouped by number of years in service of the respondents

Technology		ANOVA			F	Sig.
		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square		
t1	Between Groups	1.644	3	.548	.398	.755
	Within Groups	151.479	110	1.377		
	Total	153.123	113			
t2	Between Groups	7.861	3	2.620	1.826	.147
	Within Groups	157.893	110	1.435		
	Total	165.754	113			
t3	Between Groups	2.153	3	.718	.492	.689
	Within Groups	160.452	110	1.459		
	Total	162.605	113			
t4	Between Groups	2.230	3	.743	.589	.623
	Within Groups	138.718	110	1.261		
	Total	140.947	113			

Table 3.i. presents the significant difference in the extent of implementation of Distance Learning Delivery in terms of instruction when grouped by number of years in service of the respondents. Data shows that these instructional practices such as module, online, television and radio-based teaching are not important to teachers. This is because they have their own way of teaching the learners. Further, teachers stressed that learners are already bored with modules and a number of learners without gadgets so online learning is not appreciated by them.

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Table 3.i. Significant Difference in the Extent of Implementation of Distance Learning Delivery in terms of instruction when grouped by number of years in service of the respondents

Instruction		ANOVA			F	Sig.
		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square		
i1	Between Groups	.405	3	.135	1.885	.136
	Within Groups	7.884	110	.072		
	Total	8.289	113			
i2	Between Groups	.854	3	.285	.614	.607
	Within Groups	51.006	110	.464		
	Total	51.860	113			
i3	Between Groups	.571	3	.190	.429	.733
	Within Groups	48.876	110	.444		
	Total	49.447	113			
i4	Between Groups	.871	3	.290	.335	.800
	Within Groups	95.313	110	.866		
	Total	96.184	113			

Table 3.j. presents the significant difference in the extent of implementation of Distance Learning Delivery in terms of assessment when grouped by the number of years in service of the respondents. Table shows that, at 0.05 level of significance. Data shows that assessment of learning through printed and written tests are still very valuable to teachers whatever the situation is. This type of assessment has long been treasured and applied even in the national examinations. Thus, assessment no.1 which is distribution of printed test and written examination is always possible.

Table 3.j. Significant Difference in the Extent of Implementation of Distance Learning Delivery in terms of assessment when grouped by number of years in service of the respondents

Assessment		ANOVA			F	Sig.
		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square		
a1	Between Groups	1.138	3	.379	3.130	.029
	Within Groups	13.327	110	.121		
	Total	14.465	113			
a2	Between Groups	1.309	3	.436	.467	.586
	Within Groups	74.130	110	.674		
	Total	75.439	113			
a3	Between Groups	3.013	3	1.004	1.228	.303
	Within Groups	89.934	110	.818		
	Total	92.947	113			
a4	Between Groups	.433	3	.144	.445	.721
	Within Groups	35.672	110	.324		
	Total	36.105	113			
a5	Between Groups	2.367	3	.789	.963	.413
	Within Groups	90.098	110	.819		
	Total	92.465	113			

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Table 4. presents the problems felt by elementary and secondary teachers. Results shows that the internet connectivity whether weak, fluctuating, or no signal at all ranked first. This proves the findings that teachers had low implementation or use of smart phones, keypad cell phones and hand-held radios by teachers in a dead spot area.

Late submission of modules was caused by attitude of learners, no parents and guardians to assist the children at home, residence of learners, and educational attainment of parents hence they were hard up in teaching their children at home, and lastly, unanswered modules also contributed to the delay or late submission of modules.

For learners with abled parents, data shows that the later were the ones answering the modules. Thus, during guarded summative test, learners got low and found to be frustration level readers and cannot comprehend what they read.

With these problems felt by the teachers, the intervention program to strengthen/intensify the implementation of Distance Learning Delivery are the following: 1) workshop of teachers and other tools needed by the Generation Alpha or the 21st century -born learners. Based from DepEd Order No. 34, s. 2022, full distance learning or blended learning can still be adopted during the first quarter (August 22, 2022 to October 31, 2022). The skills gained approach can also be practiced as it is cost-wise and fastest way of teachers' literacy and learning.

Table 4. Problems felt by Elementary and Secondary teachers

Problems felt by Elementary and Secondary Teachers During DLD	Frequency
1. Internet Connectivity-slow internet, no signal	26
2. Late submission of modules	20
3. Unanswered modules – some parts	16
4. Modules are answered by parents/siblings	14
5. Hard to reach learners/distance/Risky Roads	12
6. No gadgets for some learners/ICT materials	7
7. Poor reading/Comprehension	5
8. Low scores of learners in the summative test	3
9. Parents are hard up in teaching their children	2

4.0 Conclusion

Ninety percent (90%) of the female teacher 3 who served for less than 10 years up to 20 years in the department actively participated in the implementation of distance learning delivery. Thus, transportation was their problem during the distribution and retrieval of modules from the learners in the different barangays.

The pedagogies implemented by teachers were the distribution of printed modules, calling learners individually, and teacher-parent-learner instruction. Pedagogies with low implementation by teachers were the use of audio or video learning materials and group chats/messenger as they need strong and stable internet connectivity for sending by teachers and downloading by learners. However, teachers in schools with no internet connectivity used two-way radios or home visitation observing health protocols. Teachers did not use pedagogies like the use of virtual classroom, use of applications such as KineMaster, Filmix, and the like and output video for performance tasks. For technology, the use of computer and laptop were moderately used by teachers during the distance learning delivery. Data reveals low implementation or use of smart phone, keypad cell phones and

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hand-held radios during instruction because internet connectivity is not possible in their respective areas. In terms of instruction, modules were moderately used by teachers during the distance learning. This is because this mode of instruction was chosen by School Division of Ifugao. Teachers did not use online, television, and radio-based instruction in Tinoc District. This is due to weak internet signals and absence of radio stations in the area. On assessment, teachers moderately used distribution of printed test with written examinations together with the use of printers, photocopiers, desktop computers or laptops. Google forms, outputs in video, Kotobe, and Word Wall were not utilized by the teachers during the distance learning delivery because they require workshops. However, these were used by few ICT-abled teachers.

The significant difference in the extent of implementation of Distance Learning Delivery in terms of pedagogy when grouped by gender reveals a significant difference on the use of distribution of printed modules and modules shared through an application. When grouped by gender, technology has no significance to both male and female teachers who used computers and laptops. The gadgets are not gender-specific. When grouped by gender, the indicators of instruction are not significant to teachers or instructions are not gender-focused. The assessment when grouped by gender has no significant difference or type of assessment is not classified for male and female teachers. The pedagogies when grouped by position reveals a significant difference based from the position of teachers especially on the distribution of printed modules and use of group chat or messenger. There is no significant difference in the extent of implementation of Distance Learning Delivery in terms of technology when grouped by position. Technology can possibly be used by all teachers regardless of position they held. Assessment when grouped by position has significant difference between groups of teachers who used printed test and written examination which is dependent per position. There is a significant difference in the extent of implementation of Distance Learning Delivery in terms of pedagogy when grouped by number of years in service particularly on teacher-parent-learner interaction. Interaction of teachers depends on their number of years in service. Teachers valued the importance of interaction between teachers with parents and learners. There is no significant difference in the extent of implementation of Distance learning Delivery in terms of technology when grouped by number of years in service. Teachers serving through the years are still the real instruments of learning among the young learners. There is no significant difference in the extent of implementation of distance learning delivery in terms of assessment when grouped by number of years in service. Assessment of learning through printed and written tests are still very valuable to teachers. Thus, they proved that distribution of printed test and written examination is always best way of assessing learning.

Late submission of modules was caused by attitude of learners, no parents and guardians to assist the children at home, residence of learners, and educational attainment of parents hence they were hard up in teaching their children at home, and lastly unanswered modules also contributed to the delay or late submission of modules.

There were problems felt by the respondents during the implementation of Distance Learning Delivery. Learners let their modules found to be frustration level readers and did not demonstrate instructional reading level.

The proposed intervention program is to strengthen/intensify the skills of teachers are rigid workshop and coach-mentee approach.

5.0 Contributions of Authors

The author encoded the final write-up of the study and took charge in the validation of data gathered.

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7.0 Conflict of Interests

There was no conflict of interest experienced by the researcher.

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